

SMART ERA PROJECT - EIP AGRI PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

BREAKING DATA SILOS IN RURAL TOURISM DESTINATION

Surrounded by the Tramuntana mountain range and the Mediterranean Sea, the **Valley of Sóller** is a rural territory that **relies heavily on tourism, but also on agriculture** (especially with the production of citrics and **olives**), as main economic drivers. The **high seasonality** of these sectors, combined with a high degree of **tourism massification** and a **decline of the traditional agricultural sector**, are generating important socioeconomic issues. This is exacerbated by a **brain drain phenomenon**, causing negative demographic growth, and by **poor digitalisation** and **lack of data sharing** in the region: connectivity is still a major issue; low offer of digital services by municipality and local companies; lack of knowledge and competences in technology and innovation of local stakeholders; limited availability of data, and extremely low level of data-sharing and integration between local stakeholders.

The project aims to address these challenges through digitalisation of the local industrial ecosystem, and through the implementation of digital services and activities that contribute to improving the sustainable development of the town while retaining the local population and enhancing the coexistence between residents and tourists. In particular, the project aims to **foster data sharing between the tourism and agricultural sectors**, enabling the **monitoring of key indicators**, the **identification of new products, services and business models** that could contribute to diversification of the local economy and a better distribution all year-round. As such, a **data platform** will be implemented for stakeholders to share their data, and **specific training programmes** will

GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION

be implemented to upskill local workforce and raise knowledge and awareness on digitalization, innovation, and sustainability, among others. This will contribute to **increasing the digital literacy of the population**, and to **ensuring the success and uptake** of the digital services to be provided within the municipality.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

One of the main **challenges** to carrying out the project concerns the **unshared and uncoordinated vision** among the different sectors and stakeholders. There is no, or very little cooperation among them. However, the implementation of **codesign and cocreation workshops**, using the SMART ERA' Smart Innovation Package toolkit (SIP toolkit), **greatly helped** to gather stakeholders and discuss the solutions and actions to be implemented. Indeed, the involvement and engagement of the local community is key for the success of such initiatives.

Another fundamental aspect is the **need to raise awareness and knowledge**. Most stakeholders do not share their data as they are unaware of its potential, benefits, and/or value, or simply because they don't know how to do it.

Tourism massification (overtourism) is becoming a significant issue.

Implementation of digital tools enabling a better monitoring and distribution of tourism flow within the territory is a must. **Integration of alternative tourism experiences** based on rural tourism, local products, and natural, cultural and historical heritage, **can contribute to improving the diversification of the tourism offerings**, and **alleviate massification** at "hot spots".

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS

[Website of MesCultura](#)

[SIP Workshop Video by AnySolution](#)

Credits @ Serra de Tramuntana World Heritage Consortium

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